

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

¹Mansurova Zarifa Olimjonovna, ²Boyniyozova Asilabonu Normominovna

¹Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, ²Samarkand foreign languages
institut

¹zarishmansurova@gmail.com, ²someonenoone1951@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810941>

Abstract. The article provides an in-depth exploration of teaching methodology, particularly in the context of Foreign Language Teaching (FLT). It emphasizes the interdisciplinary nature of methodology, integrating insights from various sciences. The use of the passive voice throughout maintains a formal tone and scholarly objectivity. The discussion encompasses the components of the educational process, the role of linguistics and psychology, and the evolution of teaching methods within FLT. The concluding remarks underscore the historical context and contribution of antecedent methods, contributing to a comprehensive overview of the subject.

Keywords: methodology, sciences, interconnected, educational process, pedagogy, linguistics, psychology, foreign language teaching (FLT), teaching methods, evolution.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'qitish metodikasi, xususan, Chet tillarini o'qitish (FLT) kontekstida chuqur o'rganilgan. U metodologiyani fanlararo xususiyatini ta'kidlaydi, turli fanlarning g'oyalarini birlashtiradi. Passiv ovozdanda foydalanish rasmiy ohang va ilmiy ob'ektivlikni saqlaydi. Munozara o'quv jarayonining tarkibiy qismlarini, tilshunoslik va psixologiyani rolini va FLT doirasida o'qitish usullari evolyutsiyasini o'z ichiga oladi. Yakuniy so'zlar tarixiy kontekstni va oldingi usullarning hissasini ta'kidlab, mavzuni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: metodologiya, fanlar, o'zaro bog'langan o'quv jarayoni, pedagogika, tilshunoslik, psixologiya, chet tillarini o'qitish (FLT), o'qitish metodikasi, evolyutsiya.

Аннотация. В статье дается углубленное исследование методики преподавания, в частности, в контексте преподавания иностранных языков (FLT). Он подчеркивает междисциплинарный характер методологии, интегрируя идеи различных наук. Использование пассивного залога повсюду сохраняет формальный тон и научную объективность. Обсуждаются компоненты образовательного процесса, роль лингвистики и психологии, а также эволюция методов обучения в рамках FLT. Заключительные замечания подчеркивают исторический контекст и вклад предшествующих методов, способствуя всестороннему обзору предмета.

Ключевые слова: методология, науки, взаимосвязанные, учебный процесс, педагогика, лингвистика, психология, обучение иностранным языкам (FLT), методы обучения, эволюция.

Introduction

Teaching methodology is a complex of sciences that study the methods of orderly interconnected activities of the teacher and students, aimed at solving educational problems, a system of purposeful teacher actions that organize the educational activities of students leading to the achievement of learning goals [1]. The methodology includes teaching methods, which include the following types: traditional, innovative, etc. The methodology of FLT (foreign language teaching) reasonably involves data from basic and related sciences in solving theoretical and practical issues of training, avoiding one-sided orientation to any one science [2]. Methodology as

a science is based on the educational process, the components of which are: teaching activities of a teacher, organization of training (goals, content, methods, techniques, and tools), educational activities of students [2].

The methodology of teaching a foreign language is understood here as a body of scientifically proven theory about the teaching of foreign languages in schools and other educational institutions. The English word "method" is also used to refer to a branch of research. Methods (methodology) as a science, it is the science of the ways or manners (methods) of teaching. Methods of teaching a foreign language is the science of methods of teaching foreign languages. It covers three (sometimes four) major issues:

- 1) The purpose of teaching a foreign language - why learn a foreign language.
- 2) The content of the training, i.e. what to teach to achieve the goal.
- 3) Teaching methods and techniques, i.e. how to learn a foreign language to achieve the goal in the most effective way and meet modern requirements.
- 4) Who to teach. It is necessary to distinguish between general research methods (general methodology) and special methods (private methodology).

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is associated with a number of other sciences - basic and related. The basic sciences include philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, psycholinguistics, linguistics, communication theory, etc. Data from related sciences are used by the methodology as a means of ensuring the effectiveness and reliability of their research. The connection with linguistics is important and necessary for the methodology. The subject of training is the teaching of speech activity on the material of the language. Linguistics, on the other hand, describes the main system properties of a particular language, formulates them in rules that are actively used by the methodology in the development of specific training models. The technique is closely related to psychology.

There are different methods of FLT:

1) The Grammar translation method is also called a classical method. This method came out when the western people world wanted to learn "foreign" languages such as Latin and Greek. The focus of GTM was on grammatical rules, the memorization of vocabulary and of various declensions and conjugations, translations of texts, and doing written exercises [3]. Characterized by memorization, GTM requires learners to memorize vocabulary, grammatical rules, and translations of texts. Translation exercises form a significant component, involving the rendering of sentences or passages between the target language and the native language. Written skills are heavily emphasized, with less attention given to oral communication.

While GTM provides a structured framework for understanding grammatical structures and literary texts, it has faced criticism for its limited emphasis on practical language use and communication skills. Modern language teaching trends increasingly advocate for more communicative and immersive approaches.

Historically, GTM has been employed in the teaching of classical languages. However, in contemporary language teaching, it is less commonly utilized, with many educators preferring methods that promote active communication and real-life language application.

2) The Direct Method. The basic principle of the Direct Method was that the second language learning should be more like first language learning. The method would comprise a great deal of oral interaction, spontaneous use of language, no translation between the first and the second languages, and little or no analysis of grammar rules [3]. Benefits of the Direct Method include the promotion of natural language learning, enhanced oral proficiency, and contextual

understanding of grammar and vocabulary. However, criticisms often revolve around its potential lack of systematic grammar instruction and challenges in universal application to various languages or educational settings. Overall, the Direct Method aligns with the goal of fostering practical language skills through immersive and communicative learning experiences.

3) Communicative Language Teaching. There are many ways to teach language. One is called Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). This method is learner-centered and emphasizes communication and real-life situations [3]. Key characteristics include a learner-centered approach, where instruction is tailored to meet the individual needs and interests of learners, and the primary goal is to develop effective communication skills.

4) The Audio-lingual Method (also known as the army method, the aural-oral method, or the new key), is a method of foreign language teaching in which the students learn language by repeating/imitating the recurring patterns/dialogues of everyday situations by a succession of drills. The Audio-lingual Method strongly dominated the field of education in the 1950s and 1960s [3]. The benefits of the Audio-lingual Method include the development of strong aural and oral skills, the establishment of language habits through repetitive practice, and the provision of a structured learning environment. However, criticisms have been raised, citing potential limitations in fostering creativity and preparing learners for diverse real-world communication scenarios. In essence, the Audio-lingual Method represents an approach that prioritizes the development of oral proficiency and habit formation through repetitive drills and audio-visual materials. While effective in certain contexts, its structured nature may limit its application in fostering creative language use and adaptability to various communication situations.

Conclusion

The foreign language teaching method is the product of the social development in different historical periods. The emergence of each new teaching method marks the change of the society and the development of the theories of adjacent subjects, marginal subjects, and interdisciplinary subjects. However, the emergence of any school of pedagogy is the result of inheriting the experience of predecessors, concentrating the theories of related disciplines and the experience and wisdom of the vast number of practical workers, which has been gradually formed through long-term accumulation. Although, in today's view, the early translation method and direct method have some defects, their contributions to the establishment and development of foreign language teaching theories and methods are undeniable. For example, the direct method creates its own system in the anti-translation law, the conscious-comparative method and the cognitive method inherit the grammar translation method and the audiolingual method, audio-visual method then developed the direct method. There are other schools that draw on the strengths of different schools and create more reasonable teaching systems through integration and optimization, such as the method of conscious practice and the method of function, etc. Therefore, it is not right to unilaterally talk about the advantages and disadvantages of any method regardless of history.

REFERENCE

1. Method of teaching in pedagogy: disclosure of the concept – Text: electronic. – URL: <https://zachnik.com/spravochnik/pedagogika/teorija-obuchenija/metodobuchenija-v-pedagogike/>
2. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a scientific field – Text: electronic. – URL: https://studme.org/167135/pedagogika/metodika_obucheniya_inostrannym_yazykam_nauchnaya_oblast

3. Nurhayati Lusi, Ling M .App., SupriyantiNury, Triastuti M. A. Anita. Teaching English as Foreign Language Methodology (TESOL). –2008 – pp. 26 – 28. Text: electronic. – URL: http://staff.uny.ac.id/sites/default/files/TEFL%20Methodolog%20diktat_0.pdf
4. Stepanova Anna Vyacheslavovna-THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING: GENERAL OVERVIEW- URL/https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/100459/1/978-5-91256-521-2_2021_049.pdf
5. KasimkhodjaevaMutabarAlimjanovna- FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY AS A THEORETICAL AND APPLIED SCIENCE- Web of scientist: International scientific research journal- May 2021.
6. Boyu Song-The Theory and Practice Analysis of Foreign Language Teaching Method Schools -2020.
7. Khusamiddinova Malika-METHODS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS A SCIENCE-Journal DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra> -March 2021.